

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Report on the advocacy actions 2

Work Package 7, Deliverable D7.17

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

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List of Acronyms

AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)
BCC	Bristol City Council
Borghi	I Borghi piu Belli D'Italia
BSYV	Bristol Somali Youth Voice
BUAS	Breda University of Applied Sciences
CE	Collaborative Environment
CO	Citizen Observatory
COs	Citizen Observatories
CObs	Citizen Observers
CS	Citizen Science
EBLN	The East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood
GA	Grant Agreement
GO	GREENGAGE Observatory
GOs	GREENGAGE Observatories
EU	European Union
IA	Innovation Action
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KWMC	Knowle West Media Centre
PNRR	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
UWE	University of the West of England

Glossary

Active intermediation	GREENGAGE seeks to intermediate between public authorities and citizens, green initiatives, researchers, tech providers and other potential stakeholders of Observatories. Mediating here is the process of enabling authorities of urban policy making to democratically respond to a community's understanding of the local needs for effective and sustainable innovation. This includes the navigation of legal and regulatory requirements, the negotiation of appropriate institutional arrangements, the mobilisation of resources and the facilitation of active participation of citizens in decision-making processes of urban planning. GREENGAGE Observatories will enable the active dialogue between authorities and communities by co-designed observation and analysis of real-world environments. Through active intermediation with the Pilot's situations, GREENGAGE Observatories will shape policy innovation in five different contexts of urban planning. Through active intermediation coordinators of the GREENGAGE Observatories aim to meet the needs of communities and serve the improvement of their well-being through the process and its outcomes (cf. May & Perry, 2017, p. 24).
Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories	Coordinators of GREENGAGE Observatories are those participants that deliver the Innovation Action (IA). To demonstrate innovation, these coordinators have to ensure that the urban challenges are communicated as defined by top-down perspectives (e.g., EU policies, academic expertise, project frameworks). Therefore, they regulate their co-examination by providing methodologies, communication platforms, templates, checklists, surveys, consent forms and frameworks for specification. These coordinators develop Observatories and therefore can be identified as work package leads, technology providers, the local planning agents and expand beyond the project including other stakeholders of the experiments.
Experimentation	The GREENGAGE approach on experimentation is working in the open, structured by an iterative process of co-creation. Different to other urban experiments, COs are practising

	collective learning for intelligible, ethical and democratic transitions towards urban sustainability.
GREENGAGE Observatory	A GREENGAGE Observatory is a civic Observatory designed to support collective learning, narrative change-making, and participatory governance around challenges for more sustainable, equitable and inclusive ways of urban, rural and regional planning. It functions as a citizen science-based space where local planning agents, together with researchers, technology providers and other stakeholders collaborate with local communities to observe, document, and respond to environmental, social-economic issues in their territory.
Citizen Science	“In Citizen Science, a broad network of people collaborates. Participants provide experimental data and facilities for researchers, raise new questions and co-create a new scientific culture. While they add value, volunteers acquire new learning and skills and gain a deeper understanding of the scientific work in appealing ways. As a result of this open, networked and transdisciplinary scenario, science-society-policy interactions are improved, leading in turn to a more democratic research, based on evidence and informed decision-making” (Socientize consortium, 2014, p. 10).
GREEN Engine	The GREEN Engine consists of the Collaborative Environment, the GREENGAGE Toolbox and the GO knowledge assets, also known as GO Enablers. The GREEN Engine is the mechanism that drives co-creation of evidence-based interventions (such as campaigns among others) based on the provided tools and knowledge assets.
GREENGAGE Academy	The GREENGAGE Academy hosts the emerging GREENGAGE Community of Practise and is the central platform for sharing understandings of the process of developing GREENGAGE COs. As such, the Academy serves as the central interaction platform between CO coordinators, Citizen Observers and other participants of COs. The Academy acts as a knowledge base and toolbox around the setting up and effective coordination of citizen observatories. The Academy stores and indexes training resources, MOOCs, success stories, findings and best practises collected from the four GREENGAGE pilots as well as generated or adapted to guide the setting up of the pilots.
Innovation Action	Horizon Europe Innovation Action projects are "primarily consisting of activities directly aiming at producing plans and arrangements or designs for new, altered or improved products, processes or services. For this purpose, they may include prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation and market replication. [...] Projects may include limited research and development activities” (EU HORIZON 2020). For GREENGAGE Observatories this means participatory research for innovation is not the focus but a means for understanding the GREENGAGE Innovation Action collectively.
Living Labs	According to the European Network of Living Labs, “Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments using iterative feedback processes throughout a lifecycle approach of an innovation to create sustainable impact. They focus on co-creation, rapid prototyping & testing and scaling-up innovations & businesses, providing (different types of) joint-value to the involved stakeholders.”
Thematic Co-Explorations	Thematic co-explorations are the processes that structure situated, co-created experiments and related interventions during PILOTING based on defined use cases. A GREENGAGE Observatory runs several thematic co-explorations during the lifespan of its situated experimentation.
Storytelling	Aligned with the New European Bauhaus initiative, GREENGAGE employs narrative building and storytelling in the context of urban design and practice as multi-medial, creative tools, that inspire change in ways that are inclusive, sustainable, and aesthetically engaging.

Overview of GREENGAGE Dissemination Materials

A4 Promotional Poster	The digital A4 promotional poster provides a high-level overview of the GREENGAGE project. Specifically, the poster contains some essential information on the GREENGAGE project, such as its mission and the overview of the GREENGAGE Observatories included in the project. The poster is provided in different languages.
Foldable leaflet	The digital foldable leaflet provides the general information on the project and its activities. The leaflet also depicts integral parts of the GREENGAGE toolbox, where Observers (and other stakeholders) may inform themselves on the considered technologies from the GREENGAGE repertoire. The leaflet is provided in different languages.
GREENGAGE Observatories Factsheet	Digital A4 factsheet booklet introducing GREENGAGE Innovation Pilots and their Observatories offers concise and comprehensive information on core aspects behind each of the pilots. The booklet is provided as a PDF document. The booklet starts with the description of the innovation pilots, their general position marked on the map of Europe, and their role in the GREENGAGE project, specifically focusing on their aim to promote co-created Citizen Observatories as a part of a participatory governance process. Each following page is dedicated to a specific pilot city, offering a snapshot of key information such as the pilot's geographical location, its scale (i.e., a neighbourhood, a region, or a rural community), its vision, the existing data gaps, the identified use cases, and the considered technologies from the GREENGAGE repertoire.
Roll-Up Banner	The roll-up banner summarizes the essential information about the project. Core project goals are highlighted for quick reference, alongside a dedicated QR code and a web link directing the audience to the project's contact page for further engagement and inquiries. The roll-up banner is provided in different languages.
T-Shirt Design	The T-shirt design was specifically created for use during project-organized ideathons and datathons, serving as a visual identifier that reinforces the GREENGAGE brand and highlights its funding support. The design prominently features the GREENGAGE logo and relevant funding information to ensure clear project visibility.

Executive summary (publishable)

This deliverable examines the role of advocacy actions for the uptake of GREENGAGE Observatories as instruments for local governance and policy innovation through public engagement. It provides a concise overview of past and ongoing advocacy practices, as well as planned initiatives for the near future.

At the heart of this work are the pilot's distinctive efforts of implementing Observatories as place-based processes, engaging with different publics to enable platforms for co-creating transdisciplinary knowledge and shaping public discourse that can intervene in local planning processes and discourses. At the same time, this deliverable highlights the challenges of aligning these efforts with governance priorities.

The findings of this deliverable advocate for an approach that prioritises community agency, cross-sector collaboration, and iterative learning. This includes fostering more inclusive co-design processes, integrating storytelling and social science perspectives more effectively, and strengthening civic infrastructures that enable long-term, meaningful public participation in policymaking and urban transformation.

Related documents

All GREENGAGE deliverables that are related to this document are listed below and are available at the GREENGAGE website <https://www.greengage-project.eu/knowledge-base/deliverables/>.

- D2.1 GREENGAGE CO Methodological framework.
- D2.4 Smart Governance Models 1
- D2.5 Smart Governance Models 2
- D3.2 CO Solution mapping to pilots, recruitment, and training report
- D3.3 GREENGAGE CO Academy Roadmap
- D4.1 GREEN Engine and manual 1
- D4.2 GREEN Engine and manual 2
- D4.9 GREEN Engine and manual 3
- D5.1 GREENAGE Piloting and Citizen Observer Activities Report 1
- D5.2 GREENAGE Piloting and Citizen Observer Activities Report 2
- D5.3 GREENGAGE Training and Campaigning Report and Community Building 1
- D5.5 GREENGAGE CO Academy Structured Content 1
- D6.7 GREENGAGE based Citizen Observatory – White Book for PAs 1
- D7.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results 1
- D7.2 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results 2
- D7.3 Plan for the communication, dissemination and exploitation of results 3
- D7.6 Package of Dissemination Materials 1
- D7.7 Package of Dissemination Materials 2
- D7.8 Package of Dissemination Materials 3
- D7.9 Package of Dissemination Materials 4
- D7.12 Citizen Observer's Exchange Programme 1
- D7.16 Report on the Advocacy Actions 1

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aimed to promote innovative governance processes, and tried to help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project leveraged citizens' participation and equipped them with innovative digital solutions that shall transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, the aim was to inspire citizens to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The idea was to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This was facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories were and are a place where pilot cities co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up processes with top-down perspectives. This provides the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aimed to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The Citizens Observatory campaigns were deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano Valley (Italy), Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aimed to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which should complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of the GREENGAGE project.

2 Object of the Deliverable

This deliverable, together with its first version (D7.16), summarizes and examines the role of advocacy actions for the uptake of GREENGAGE Observatories as instruments for local governance and policy innovation through public engagement. It weaves together reflections on carried out advocacy efforts, offering a comprehensive view of how these actions support the long-term sustainability and impact of the GREENGAGE Observatories.

Through a narrative grounded in collective reflexivity, this report highlights both the distinctive Observatories that emerged in pilot's localities up to now and how they have prepared themselves for entering public discourse, amplifying diverse voices, and contributing to governance debates. By drawing on situated knowledges and drafting tailored narratives for change, this document advocates for a more co-creative approach to strategies that centre the pilot owner's agency, transdisciplinary learning through practices of collective reflexion, and interdisciplinary collaboration beyond the GREENGAGE.

3 Introduction

In GREENGAGE, advocacy actions encompass activities designed to promote the adoption of Citizen Observatories as tools for participatory governance and the uptake of their results by policymakers and other stakeholders to collaboratively enact the objectives of the European Green Deal. These efforts aim to identify and address barriers to local adoption, organise discursive interventions to influence policy, and enhance the project's impact and legacy.

The preparation work for the uptake of GREENGAGE Observatories unfolded on two interrelated levels: the **overarching Innovation Action** and the **pilot-level implementation**. This process was inherently dynamic, iterative, and multi-layered, evolving through what we termed *policy and governance labs*. These labs served as experimental spaces where Observatories were developed in collaboration with pilot partners, tested through efforts of pilot owners, and refined by their interaction with local publics.

While GREENGAGE provided a conceptual and technological framework to guide Observatory development, their actual uptake depended on the pilots' abilities and aspirations to engage diverse publics. This engagement was shaped by each pilot's specific capabilities, opportunities, and constraints – factors beyond the project's direct control. To navigate this complexity, the project focused on laying a strong foundation for experimentation around public engagement at the project level. This involved ensuring that **GREENGAGE Observatories were introduced and discussed as evolving processes and innovative platforms for participatory governance and policy making**. In chapter 4 we reflect on key activities performed on the project level to achieve that.

On the pilot's level, the uptake of Observatories as instruments for participatory governance and policy making was emphasising the **iterative development** of the pilot's Observatory and its distinctive citizen science initiatives. **Through engaging different publics and applying practices, tools and technologies for active intermediation, the real-world possibilities for driving innovation became more tangible over the time of preparing and piloting with GREENGAGE Observatories**. In chapter 5 we pitch the four Observatories' with an emphasis on narratives that appeal to funders and other political influencers while grounding their purpose and innovation potentials in the socio-political contexts of the pilots.

Key to the efforts undertaken in relation to this report was to understand the actual meaning of **advocacy actions** in GREENGAGE, based on a synthesis of efforts on the project and the pilot implementation level. We understand that these actions take two primary forms:

- 1) **Building public support for Citizen Observatories** – Encouraging policymakers, institutions, and the broader public to see Citizen Observatories as essential instruments for advancing inclusive governance, particularly in alignment with the objectives of the European Green Deal.
- 2) **Stakeholder engagement for participatory research and innovation** – Facilitating debates and discussions on public concerns through pilot-specific campaigns, which serve as live demonstrations of Observatories in action.

Storytelling facilitates public engagement by integrating and simplifying complex data into relatable narratives that inspire, educate, and mobilize communities. Research shows that stories enhance understanding by combining facts with emotional resonance, making difficult concepts more accessible, while encouraging empathy and collective action (Green & Brock, 2000; Dahlstrom, 2014). By integrating personal experiences, cultural narratives, and multimedia formats, storytelling fosters deeper connections between data, policy discussions, and lived realities (Polletta et al., 2011).

Storytelling plays a central role in GREENGAGE's approach to embedding Citizen Observatories into governance and policymaking as it facilitates the engagement with different publics and their arenas. As Observatories aim to shape public discourses and prompt collaborative action towards a green and just transition, storytelling serves as a powerful method for a) **advancing public engagement in urban and regional planning through the Citizen Observatory paradigm** and b) **organising discursive**

interventions based on participatory research that the pilots are coordinating. Aligned with the *New European Bauhaus* initiative, GREENGAGE employs narrative building and storytelling in the context of urban design and practice as multi-medial, creative tools, that inspire change in ways that are inclusive, sustainable, and aesthetically engaging.

GREENGAGE aims to follow the principles of *upstream engagement*, as outlined in the EU's *Responsible Research and Innovation* framework, ensuring that communities participate early in shaping research and policy. This participatory approach aligns with the UK National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement's (NCCPE) definition of public engagement as a *two-way process* – one that involves **interaction, listening, and generating mutual benefits**.

A key method in this approach is **co-creating stories with data**, where stakeholders collaboratively analyse data and construct narratives that reflect shared experiences and concerns. This process humanizes abstract numbers, ensuring that underrepresented voices are heard and policy discussions become more inclusive (Couldry & Hepp, 2017). Techniques such as participatory action research workshops and interactive data visualisations bridge the gap between data and lived experience, empowering communities to take an active role in making sense of data and co-producing assets that influence public discourse and inform governance frameworks (Bounegru et al., 2017). In alignment with this, **Datathon events** appear as a milestone for increasing capacity for the uptake of Observatories, as they merge key advocacy actions, bring stakeholders from different sectors together and make an Observatory experienceable. As they are an exemplar for further developing practices, tools and tech in response to the situational understanding of pilots – and therefore the GREENGAGE approach on Observatories – we use Chapter 6 to reflect on these multi-stakeholder events.

Recognizing and addressing barriers to public engagement remains central to developing these Observatories within policy and governance labs. Chapter 7 elaborates on some **challenges identified across pilots and how they were or could be addressed**. To understand the challenges for the uptake of Observatories and realisation of advocacy actions, we started with reflexive conversations with pilot owners in early February 2025. From these conversations we understood that the challenges are, in part, based on the situational conditions in the pilot localities and these were addressed in previous reports (D5.1, D5.2).

Chapter 8 concludes with suggestions on further iterative adjustments to foster broader project impact, ensuring meaningful multi-stakeholder engagement and long-term integration of Observatories into local governance processes and arenas of public debate.

4 Preparing for the uptake of GREENGAGE Observatories as instruments for policy and governance innovation

In the following, we describe the multifaced efforts undertaken by the **Innovation Action as a whole**, to lay a foundation for public engagement on the project level, ensuring that GREENGAGE Observatories are introduced and discussed in relevant arenas as processes and platforms for participatory governance and policy innovation. These efforts are integral to shaping and strengthening the project's advocacy activities, as they help build awareness, foster stakeholder dialogue, and drive policy engagement.

Laying out the groundwork

In the beginning of the project, we delivered conceptual frameworks that aimed to establish a common GREENGAGE baseline that should inform all Observatories (WP2/WP6). Aiming for a coherent, yet situated approach on stakeholder engagement, knowledge co-creation and dissemination, we developed the **GREENGAGE Academy**, including “train-the-trainers” assets for the pilot owners (WP3, D3.3). With the ambition to ensure data-driven knowledge co-creation, we developed the **GREEN Engine** (WP4, D4.1, D4.2, and D4.9) as a central repository of digital and analogue applications, templates and other knowledge assets for citizen science initiatives – or the technological framework.

Simultaneously, the project developed a comprehensive plan for impactful public communication and dissemination (WP7, D7.3) that seek to demonstrate the GREENGAGE approach on Observatories through different ways of interacting with publics. These efforts can be understood as preparational work to engage in advocacy actions – or activities that ensure the buy in from stakeholders with political influence and increase general public support for the uptake of Observatories as tools for participatory governance and policy making. The evaluation metrics developed in task 7.6 of the project, define that for this to happen, **GREENGAGE needed to engage in governance innovation debates on an ongoing basis**. For this to be successful, project representatives committed to share insights in at least 5 panels or presentations on urban governance innovation. Beyond that, the project ‘s outputs needed to engage in thematic discourses and for this to be successful, representatives needed to engage in at least 15 thematic events around key project themes to share and increase their understandings on piloting with GREENGAGE Observatories as platforms for knowledge co-creation and dissemination.

To further support this, project partners identified key **categories for organising and documenting dissemination activities** (WP7) and **structuring public knowledge assets in the GREENGAGE Academy** (WP5). Efforts were made to establish a clear **visual identity and branding strategy of the project**, ensuring consistent use of logos and design assets across the consortium (WP7). To expand public reach, we launched our **project website** and **social media channels** while reassessing the effectiveness of channels such as X (formerly Twitter). The X channel was subsequently phased out as other communication avenues proved to be more effective for achieving the project's communication goals. Likewise, a need for additional channel emerged, the one that would reach a non-academic audience. Accordingly, we launched a dedicated **Instagram** project account to enhance our outreach efforts. To make the project more tangible, the team published first **interviews with Observers** from the Turano Valley Observatory and began preparing **quarterly e-newsletters**. To enhance public awareness as GREENGAGE, the consortium produced **digital leaflets, brochures, and a promotional video trailer**, alongside **webinars** designed to introduce the GREENGAGE Academy. Given the diversity of pilots' specifics, the team began after the first iteration of piloting opting for tailored assets rather than standardised templates, allowing for greater flexibility in developing Observatories to become meaningful for the interaction with publics to foster impactful change of the pilot's situations and a legacy of GREENGAGE.

Public dissemination and knowledge transfer

Meanwhile, **knowledge transfer and public dissemination efforts advanced ongoing activities of conceptualising and sharing** messages about the GREENGAGE approach on Citizen Observatories and made possible to discuss these with the project peers and get feedback from the distinctive communities of interest. These efforts included drafting **scientific publications** for high-impact journals and conferences (Table 1), as well as representing GREENGAGE at major events (Table 2). The project was introduced at the **Bristol Business Breakfast 2023, International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies (SPLITECH) 2023, and European Conference on Software Architecture (ECSA) 2024**, with workshops addressing key topics such as diversity and inclusivity in citizen science. The consortium also contributed to panels and workshops at **EuroGEO workshop 2023, Nordic Environmental Social Science Conference (NESS) 2024**, at the quadrennial joint meeting of the **European Association for the Study of Science and Technology (EASST) and the Society for Social Studies of Science (4S) (EASST-4S) 2024**, presenting on methodologies for Citizen Observatories and the role of discursive interventions in policy innovation, but also the annual **POLIS 2024** conference – a leading sustainable urban mobility event targeting cities and regions. Joint activities were initiated with **sister projects**, including **EuroGEO and ECSA**, and the **annual EURA International Relocation Congress 2025**'s panel on healthy and sustainable cities. These joint efforts will continue beyond the duration of the project, culminating in a joint workshop at **ECSA 2026**. The collaboration with sister projects is especially important to build a community of practice that is developing Citizen Observatories that will help to establish the approach on an EU governance level. Additionally, the team actively participated in trans local governance innovation discussions, contributing to panels at **Open Living Lab Day's (OLLD) 2023 and 2024**, focusing on **Living Labs and Smart Communities**. Further dissemination efforts were carried out within the framework of for **Change Now Summit 2025, Waves of Change 2025, EURA Congress 2025**, alongside a continued commitment to hosting and participating in thematic events across key project areas. The most prominent of such events was the **SSPRC 2025** conference – **Smart and Sustainable Planning for Cities and Regions**, where the first public dissemination of the GREENGAGE White Book took place.

Table 1: List of GREENGAGE scientific publications.

Title of the scientific publication	Authors	Event name
Designing Interactive Analytics Dashboards for Diverse Target Groups: The Process and Decision-making	Milena Vuckovic, Dawid Wolosiuk, Johanna Schmidt	9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2024
Democratizing co-production of thematic coexplorations for Citizen Observatories	Diego López-de-Ipiña, Mikel Emaldi, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Dawid Wolosiuk, Felipe Vergara, Jan Peters-Anders	9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2024
Performance Assessment of Wearable Atmotube Pro Sensor for Air Quality Citizen Science Applications	Alejandro Pujante Perez, Eduardo Illueca Fernandez, Syed Mohsin Ali Shah, Diego Casado-Mansilla, Antonio Jesus Jara Valera, Diego Lopez-de-Ipina	9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2024

Enhancing Citizen Science Engagement Through Gamification: A Case Study of the SOCIO-BEE project	Felipe Vergara; Cristian Olivares-Rodríguez; Mariluz Guenaga; Diego López-De-Ipiña; Maite Puerta-Beldarrain; Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera	9th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2024
Leveraging LLMs for Smart Cities Qualitative Data Analysis	Elisa Covato, Kamran Soomro, Zaheer Khan, Muhammad Bilal, Sam Kirby, and Tom Yiangou	17th International Symposium on Intelligent Distributed Computing 2024
Towards a Methodological Framework for Citizen Observatories to Promote Inclusive Urban Governance	Julia Costa Carneiro, Milena Vuckovic, Anna Kozłowska, Nikolas Serrano, Zaheer Khan, Diego López-De-Ipiña, Jan Peters-Anders, David Ludlow, Sjors Martens, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Andrii Khrystodulov, Dawid Wolosiuk, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer	16th NESS - Nordic Environmental Social Science Conference
Empowering Urban Transformation: The Role of Citizen Observatories in Inclusive and Data-Driven Governance	Anna Kozłowska, Milena Vuckovic, Zaheer Khan, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer, Elisa Covato, Sjors Martens, Francisco Sanz, Diego López-De-Ipiña, Jan Peters-Anders	REAL CORP 2025 – 30th International Conference on Urban Planning and Regional Development in the Information Society
Participatory Design of Visual Analytics Tools for Different Target Groups	Milena Vuckovic, Johanna Schmidt, Dawid Wolosiuk	Journal of Communications Software and Systems
An Exploratory Study of Digital Literacy and Proficiency Challenges in Citizen-Based Initiatives	Milena Vuckovic, Dawid Wolosiuk, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Diego López-De-Ipiña	10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2025
A Strategy for Enhancing Privacy and Usability of Crowdsourced Data	Dawid Wolosiuk, Milena Vuckovic, Jan Peters-Anders, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Diego López-De-Ipiña, Felipe Borge Vergara	10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2025
Validating a Citizen Observatories enabling Platform by completing a Citizen Science Loop	Diego López-De-Ipiña, Dawid Wolosiuk, Mikel Emaldi, Felipe Borge Vergara, Rubén Sánchez-Corcuera, Milena Vuckovic, Diego Casado-Mansilla, Jan Peters-Anders	10th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2025
A Systems Thinking Approach to Inclusive Governance	Rana Habibi, Amanda Ramsay, Martin Zach, Barkha Javed, Zaheer Khan	Discover Global Society, Springer Nature

Table 2: List of external events

Type of participation/Title of the talk	Authors	Event name
(NETWORKING EVENT/TALK) Innovative concept of GREENGAGE	Zaheer Khan, David Ludlow, Muhammad Bilal	Bristol Business Breakfast
(PLENARY SESSION) GREENGAGE introduction	Diego López-de-Ipiña	8th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies – SpliTech 2023
(PANEL DISCUSSION) KWMC’s Bristol Living Lab practice and a reflection on the strategic role of Living Labs in regional transitions	Carolyn Hassan, Julia Costa Carneiro, Annali Grimes	Open Living Lab Days 2023
(WORKSHOP) GREENGAGE - Promoting innovative governance and helping public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies by engaging with citizens via Citizen Observatories	Jan Peters-Anders	EUROGEO WORKSHOP 2023
(JOINT WORKSHOP CitiObs, GREENGAGE, UrbanReLeaf) Exploring ways to Enhance Diversity and Inclusivity in Citizen Science	(GREENGAGE authors) Francisco Sanz, Judith Bielsa, Milena Vuckovic, Jan Peters-Anders, Anna Kozłowska, Julia Costa Carneiro	European Citizen Science Association Conference – ECSA 2024
(MARKETPLACE BOOTH) Empowering urban transformation in an era of rapid change: CitiObs, GREENGAGE and UrbanReLeaf	(GREENGAGE authors) Jan Peters-Anders, Francisco Sanz, Milena Vuckovic, Anna Kozłowska	European Citizen Science Association Conference – ECSA 2024
(WORKSHOP) Towards a Methodological Framework for Citizen Observatories to Promote Inclusive Urban Governance	Julia Costa Carneiro, Nicolás Serrano, Diego López-de-Ipiña, Milena Vuckovic, Zaheer Khan, Jan Peters-Anders, David Ludlow, Sjors Martens, Rubén Sánchez Corcuera, Andrii Khrystodulov, Dawid Wolosiuk, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer, Anna Kozłowska	16 th NESS – Nordic Environmental Social Science Conference
(PANEL DISCUSSION) Organising discursive interventions for transformative policy making: Collective Reflexion on GREENGAGE Observatories	Julia Costa Carneiro, Sjors Martens, Milena Vuckovic, Sabine Seymour, Fani Kostourou	EASST-4S 2024
(PLENARY SESSION) GREENGAGE Cycling Lab: Citizen observatories to propagate cycling in North Brabant	Sjors Martens	2024 Annual POLIS Conference
(PANEL DISCUSSION) Smart Communities: AI, Digital Transition, and Social Change / Co-creating Civic Innovation through Arts, Tech & Care	Julia Costa Carneiro	Open Living Lab Days 2024

(PANEL DISCUSSION) Smart Village, technology at the service of Italian villages: opportunities and applications

Andrea Vignoli

ECOMONDO 2024

(LIVE BRIEF) Designing Liveable Neighbourhoods together	Julia Costa Carneiro	Live Brief 2024
(PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT) Making Liveable Neighbourhoods together	Julia Costa Carneiro	Urban Hosts 2024
(PANEL DISCUSSION) Rethinking mobility in the Ørestad neighbourhood	Julia Costa Carneiro, Rasmus Reeh, Sabine Seymour	Change Now Forum 2025
(PANEL DISCUSSION) GREENGAGE approach around engagement	Sabine Seymour	Waves of Change 2025
(PANEL DISCUSSION) Advancing Smart Governance for Sustainable Urban Transformation through Citizen Observatories and Digital Collaboration across European Cities and Regions	Julia Costa Carneiro, Stephen Hall, Zaheer Khan, Milena Vuckovic, Anna Kozłowska, Nicolás Serrano, Diego López-de-Ipiña, Annali Grimes, Zach Martin, Elisa Covato, Kamran Soomro, Jan Peters-Anders, Ernst Gebetsroither-Geringer	EURA 2025
(JOINT PANEL WITH SISTER PROJECTS) Empowering Smart Urban Governance through Citizen Observatories: EU Initiatives Driving Green and Digital Transformations for Sustainable Urban Futures	(GREENGAGE authors) Julia Costa Carneiro, Samuel Green	EURA 2025
(WORKING SESSION) GREENGAGE Observatories concept and White Book	Anna Kozłowska, Jan Peters-Anders, Zaheer Khan, Francisco Sanz, Diego López-de-Ipiña	Smart and Sustainable Planning for Cities and Regions Conference 2025

Pilot-level public engagement and narratives

At pilot level, we prepared for the uptake of GREENGAGE Observatories through exercises for public engagement a) by developing **pilot presentations tailored to audiences that are key for influencing policy and governance innovation** and b) through starting the development of public **communication strategies for the Observatories' citizen science initiatives**. While this was an ongoing effort, we undertook a series of strategic steps to help framing the pilots and – following the recommendations from our Methodological Framework (D2.1) to develop **specific methodologies for public engagement**, accordingly, alongside building networks and communities for impact.

Central to this process was the application of **Situational Analysis**, a method that helped map the socio-political landscape, identify key actors and their communication channels, and uncover barriers and opportunities for **framing GREENGAGE Observatory campaigns in response to addressed planning challenges**. To become able to build and share compelling narratives was therefore key in the preparation and our collective learning on what enables or hinders innovation towards performing the European Green Deal. Recognising the importance of reaching publics beyond the usual suspects, we started the work on narrative building with **exploring how to speak to historically underrepresented groups in policymaking** in ways that gain their buy-in to participate in local transition efforts. We explored **Persona Cards** as a tool to facilitate the understanding of different audiences, **their mindsets and lived experiences** and applied them for co-developing the narrative of the North Brabant pilot

during our 2nd consortium meeting in Autumn 2023, and then further tested and refined within a training for living lab practitioners on “co-creating civic innovation with arts, tech and care” at the Day 0 of Open Living Lab Days 2024. Pilot specific **Roadmapping workshops** helped us define pathways for local innovation with GREENGAGE Observatories, feeding into the **Pilot Specifications (D3.3)** that later evolved in **pilot’s Observatory narratives** shared in D7.16 and updated in this deliverable. Additionally, a dedicated **"Opening the Academy" workshop** sensitised consortium partners in the 3rd project meeting in Spring 2024 to the **interactive, embodied aspects of narrative building and storytelling** – highlighting the importance of balancing analogue and digital engagement and raising awareness of the **hidden politics in co-creating stories for change** using digital interaction platforms with information flowing across front-end interfaces and back-end dashboards.

We understood later that project **use cases need to support the narratives that frame the Observatories publicly** rather than the other way round. These narratives are the backbones of engaging participants in citizen science initiatives, that means they set the scene for making stories with data that are meaningful for driving changes in how local situations are understood and addressed by climate mitigation policies. Consequently, we started to refine these use cases after the first iteration of piloting and updated the participatory research protocols, called **thematic co-explorations**, accordingly several times. This iterative development was inevitable as the pilot partners had to refine their Observatory’s portfolio through the interaction with stakeholders and through identifying entry points for engaging with local discourses, responding to the emerging possibilities and barriers for making Observatories acknowledged as instrument in the local decision-making processes. A preparational component of framing **narratives for policy and governance innovation through Observatories** or refining the Observatory’s offer was understanding related discourse better and leveraging strategic relationships to influential stakeholders.

What made the idea of public engagement through Observatories more tangible were **Datathon events and other high visibility public events** to advocate for Observatories as part of local processes of policy making. Simultaneously, the **GREENGAGE app and various data visualisation and storytelling tools (WP4)** were developed in several iterations. The technological possibilities were shared within Innovation Action Board meetings to enable the integration of the GREEN Engine in planning respective engagement strategies for the 2nd iteration of piloting. Meanwhile we were fostering collaborations with local universities to build capacity for **Datathons** and exploring diverse ways for implementing the **Ambassador Exchange Programme** to support distinctive public engagement needs of the pilots.

Throughout these efforts, the consortium **explored the meaning of advocacy actions for the uptake of GREENGAGE Observatories as instruments of local policy and governance innovation**. This was happening while the pilot partners carried on with their own research and innovation efforts, developing Observatories in diverse manifestations.

5 Advocating for the uptake of GREENGAGE Observatories: Reflecting on local policy and governance innovation

In line with the GREENGAGE objective of piloting with Observatories as processes and tools for participatory local governance and policy innovation, we defined the project assets that are required for a successful uptake of the pilot's Observatories in M18-M36. In task 7.2 we identified the pilot's engagement in local discussions or debates that would be achieved once **pilot partners would have participated in 3 public debates or discussions around their innovation efforts (either in-person event or through media)**. We further defined that for the recognition of Observatories' knowledge assets in local processes of policy making it would be required that pilot representatives engage in creating and disseminating data stories. For this to be successful, we committed to **creating at least 3 data stories per pilot and disseminate each data story through at least 3 channels, such as social media and community platforms**. For more information on a conceptualisation of data stories refer to section 9.2 of this deliverable. To support the initial set of activities, which involve engaging in local discussions and debates, we have developed the pilot pitches that articulate how each Observatory has been developed as an instrument for local policy and governance innovation in its own distinctive ways.

In the first report on advocacy actions (D7.16) we have been highlighting the importance of and started pitching innovation pilots to spark interest in the public communication of these local governance and policy labs. Since, these narratives were guiding the sensemaking of co-creative experiments performed in GREENGAGE Observatories. This chapter draws on the activities performed in piloting and campaigning (D5.2) to update these visions and reflect the pilots in regard to their actual impact on local policy and governance innovation.

Tailored to resonate with interdisciplinary academics, funders, policymakers, and civil society stakeholders, this positioning aims to a) **strengthen the legitimacy of the unique Observatories to be acknowledged as GREENGAGE Observatories within the broader Innovation Action** and b) **supporting the alignment of citizen science initiatives that aim to test and demonstrate these Observatories**. They are presented in a narrative style with the intention to inform public-facing dissemination efforts on the project level such as blog posts and outreach materials on the project level. These narratives have already been shared with the wider public through the GREENGAGE website¹ and have been featured in various scientific publications, ensuring both accessibility and academic visibility.

5.1 North Brabant, NL: Validating maintenance policy through subjective data

In North Brabant Province, a rapidly growing province with one of Europe's most advanced cycling networks, the GREENGAGE pilot addressed a persistent governance challenge: the "objectivity gap" between technically well-maintained roads and how safe or comfortable they actually feel to cyclists. Despite a strong cycling culture and high-trust public institutions, the Province recognised that achieving its ambitious modal shift targets, 20% more cycled kilometres by 2027 and 40% by 2040, required more than engineering excellence. The pilot therefore reframed subjective data not as anecdotal opinion but as a vital evidence layer, positioning bikeability as a matter of public concern and establishing the Citizen Observatory as a tool for strengthening democratic legitimacy in a mature governance ecosystem.

To bridge technical assessments and cyclists lived experience, the Observatory systematically captured subjective perceptions and integrated them into the province's Digital Twin, testing whether citizen feedback could serve as a "validation foil" for engineering assessments. The emerging evidence confirmed this: most ratings aligned with or were more generous than technical scores, proving that citizens are reliable sensors of quality and that the current objective maintenance scoring is in line with citizen opinion. Where discrepancies appeared, they highlighted crucial design, safety, and comfort issues, such as visibility, lighting, traffic proximity, and intersection layouts that fall outside the scope of technical inspections. These insights demonstrated that subjective data expands institutional capacity,

¹ <https://www.greengage-project.eu/>

enabling small, targeted interventions to generate a disproportionately positive impact on cyclist satisfaction.

This repositioning of citizen-generated evidence was made possible by a dedicated governance setup. The Citizen Observatory's core team, composed of provincial officials, the Fietzersbond cyclists' union, and Breda University of Applied Sciences, acted as a joint decision-making arena where expectations were aligned, indicators co-defined, and the practical use of subjective data negotiated. Shared route explorations turned civil servants into participants who gained embodied understanding of the network. This relational work was central to the pilot's advocacy actions: it created institutional space where citizen participation was treated as constructive, not oppositional, and where public evidence could meaningfully shape maintenance priorities.

The Observatory's engagement strategy relied on a campaign-based "Cycling Lab", an approach that combined methodological rigour with event-based mobilisation and visible advocacy. The flagship Provincial Cycling Lab in Heusden (28–29 June) demonstrated the scalability of participatory monitoring by producing 97 detailed surveys in a single day and, crucially, attracting the working-age commuter demographic (40–60), a group typically missing from earlier phases. Preceding this, the GREENGAGE Ambassador Program (23–24 June) sent BUAs students to Copenhagen, where cross-pilot data collection validated interoperability of the GREENGAGE stack and stress-tested protocols that were subsequently refined. Complementary micro-campaigns, such as bollard mapping, school-route engagement through networks of 12 school directors, and a BUAs student challenge generating extensive GPS tracks, added granularity to the evidence base, revealing desire lines and priority safety corridors. An Online Engagement Drive (22 April) further broadened participation and supplied longitudinal commute data, while the Datathon was reconfigured into BUAs coursework after data-delivery delays, embedding Observatory methodology into the training of future planners rather than limiting it to a one-off event.

Together, these activities produced a robust dataset of nearly 200 reported issues, 97 full surveys, and extensive GPS tracks, evidence that carried political weight because it was co-produced with civil servants and grounded in lived experience. The insights translated directly into policy uptake: subjective heatmaps and perception scores began informing maintenance planning; the Digital Twin provided official visibility for citizen evidence; quick fixes such as bollard adjustments, foliage trimming, and intersection improvements were implemented during the pilot; and the province initiated steps to institutionalise recurring Cycling Labs and explore "user sentiment" as a KPI in contractor performance. Citizens were found to be indulgent toward minor technical imperfections but hyper-sensitive to safety failures. This finding enabled budget optimisation by deprioritising costly resurfacing where citizens felt conditions were "good enough," shifting resources instead to interventions with high subjective return on investment. The pilot also revealed institutional variation in receptiveness, with mid-sized municipalities like Heusden displaying strong uptake, while larger cities like Den Bosch, armed with rigid technical systems, proved less open to citizen science, highlighting the need for differentiated scaling strategies.

By the end of the pilot, North Brabant had demonstrated how a Citizen Observatory can transform infrastructure maintenance from a technical procedure into a shared governance challenge. It showed that subjective perceptions are legitimate, actionable, and policy-relevant; that citizens can validate and refine expert models; and that participatory monitoring can enhance transparency, responsiveness, and institutional trust. In doing so, it fulfilled core GREENGAGE advocacy objectives: opening discursive and operational space for citizen observations to influence infrastructure policy, building institutional capacity to interpret public evidence, and charting a pathway toward a more democratic, user-centred smart region where lived experience becomes a formal part of environmental and mobility decision-making. The result is a durable governance innovation in which citizen-generated data strengthens, not destabilises, the integrity and legitimacy of provincial maintenance decisions.

5.2 Bristol, UK: Bristol Civic Observatory: Prototyping restorative practices in neighbourhood planning

The Bristol Civic Observatory emerged in a moment of acute tension around the city's Liveable Neighbourhood strategy, a cornerstone of Bristol's plan to reduce motorised vehicle use by 40% by 2030. While Liveable Neighbourhoods promise cleaner air, safer streets and more active travel - backed

by strong national and local political mandates - the early selection of pilot areas failed to account for deep socio-economic inequalities. In East Bristol, particularly the diverse and economically constrained neighbourhood of Barton Hill, this misalignment intensified perceptions of a “segregated city,” fuelling distrust and vocal protest. Through the co-design of the Observatory, Bristol City Council recognised that consultation practices in contested transitions require more widespread public engagement, including those that have been felt unsheared or not reached through former consultation. In response to this reflection, Bristol City Council commissioned KWMC and PRAXIS research to design and deliver a deep engagement process with marginalised communities of a distinctive neighbourhood of the scheme area (Barton Hill) and to engage officers of Bristol City Council as well as engaged professionals working towards a just climate transition in Bristol in a transdisciplinary learning journey – all encompassed within the Bristol Civic Observatory. The Bristol Civic Observatory was created within an institutional transformation of Bristol City Council’s public engagement in planning and as a prototype for democratic innovation, co-developed by KWMC, Praxis Research, and UWE, to help the city repair strained relationships, democratise transport governance, and ensure that no community was left behind in the transition toward more sustainable mobility.

From its outset, the Observatory framed Liveable Neighbourhoods as both a public concern and an equity challenge, grounding its work in the trauma, conflict, and mistrust that planning decisions can produce - particularly in underserved communities. Barton Hill’s demographic profile underlined this necessity: high levels of deprivation, diverse linguistic communities, a young population, and residents who are disproportionately excluded by traditional, text-based, town-hall-centric consultation. Against this backdrop, the Observatory set out to “ground-truth” the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) scheme, capturing the lived experience of its early implementation period and treating community perceptions and sentiments as a dataset with equal weight to the Council’s engineering projections. Through this, the pilot explicitly sought to close the epistemic gap between strategic planning and everyday realities, demonstrating that the success of the scheme depended not only on technical design but on whether residents, especially young people, disabled people, carers, and ethnically diverse communities, felt safe, respected, and included.

To achieve this, the Observatory prototyped a series of restorative, relational and participatory methods that repositioned lived experience as legitimate expert knowledge. The approach centred on deep listening, curiosity, and empathy, replacing extractive surveys with reflexive, open-ended conversations. The team applied and tested the “Conversation Station,” a mix of hardware, software and facilitation communicated as mobile, pop-up recording studio that was invented for this purpose and served as a research tool that allowed people to contribute their experiences informally in spaces they already inhabit: youth clubs, homes, school playgrounds, health centres, arts trails, community events and street corners. Voices were turned into structured evidence through AI-supported thematic analysis and visualised in the GREENGAGE dashboards, enabling policymakers to see patterns in fear, safety, crossing challenges, mobility constraints and misinformation. Additionally, they were used as material for a piece of sound art that was shared back in several iterations with local communities and the public to ensure representation and balance of the presented perspectives before a final version will be uploaded on the EU funded online platform Audiospace by Sounding Future2 and shared via the consortium partner’s platforms – together with the policy brief the partners secured funding for.

In the heart of Bristol Civic Observatory’s work was the partnership building and co-design of neighbourhood observation campaigns with local community ambassadors and their groups: Young people contributed through co-designed “missions” and storytelling, while students at Redfield Educate Together tested mobile app-based monitoring during play street events. At Wellspring Settlement, the neighbourhood’s trusted anchor organisation, engagement with health workers and Sudanese and Somali women drivers surfaced specific mobility concerns invisible in previous planning cycles and tangible solutions for improving the scheme. Across these activities, diverse groups of residents participated, with deliberate prioritisation of groups historically excluded from public consultation processes, including the Bristol East Disabled Society and cohorts of Somali and Sudanese women whose lived mobility realities challenge dominant assumptions about modal shift.

Another key dimension of this pilot was framing the Civic Observatory as a co-creative learning journey that also involved engaged professionals working in the realm of a just transition in Bristol, as well as local civil servants and councillors that were in some ways part of co-designing, implementing and evaluating the EBLN scheme. Through treating them as participants of the Observatory, they helped

² <https://audiospace.soundingfuture.com/>

understanding the Council’s position which was key for the objective of active intermediation – the key feature of the Observatory.

Throughout this process, the Observatory functioned as a mediator between communities and the Council, and between immediate anxieties and long-term visions for a just transition. Civil servants and community groups co-created data and the overall narrative translated through a piece of sound art, making sense of conflict and ambiguity together and building psychological safety for honest exchange. The Observatory thus became a participatory monitoring and evaluation platform, a democratic innovation testbed, and a prototype for relational governance practices that aim not only to collect data but to rebuild trust. Digital tools were deployed to make sense of lived experience rather than overshadow it; qualitative insights were visualised through Superset and fed back to the Councils Transport and Active Travel teams, enabling inclusive monitoring to sit alongside sensor data.

The pilot’s impact became visible both in policy adaptation and institutional restructuring. Evidence gathered through the Observatory migrated into formal reporting pipelines: Wellspring Settlement incorporated findings into an evidence-based submission outlining impacts on health services; the Lawrence Hill Neighbourhood Forum reused AI-generated thematic insights to strengthen its own representations to the Council. The most direct outcome was the contribution to the wider evaluation on the EBLN trial design itself, where lived-experience evidence highlighted critical shortcomings in the initial approach, especially for disabled residents and those reliant on cars for essential journeys. This prompts a shift from strict implementation toward responsive adaptation, encouraging the Council to refine exemptions, improve communication, and strengthen engagement techniques for the forthcoming schemes in Bristol. The recommendations shared with the local authority and a forthcoming policy brief that will make sense from the insights through the lenses of mobility justice, highlight the potential of methodologies and digital tools developed in Barton Hill to be subsequently adopted for South Bristol’s upcoming Liveable Neighbourhood scheme. The trustful relationships built with members of the Council as well as the prototyped public-commons-partnership are signalling an institutional commitment to scaling the Observatory model city-wide. GREENGAGE’s decision to maintain the technical infrastructure post-project further ensures that the Observatory will continue to support Bristol’s long-term governance transformation.

By centring lived experience, fostering new relationships, and co-creating evidence that is both analytically rigorous and emotionally grounded, the Bristol Civic Observatory has pioneered a restorative model of neighbourhood planning. It demonstrates how inclusive monitoring can reshape public discourse, elevate marginalised voices, and repair strained relationships between communities and the local authority. As a governance innovation, it moves Bristol beyond extractive consultation toward a continuous, trust-building dialogue where street-level experience becomes a formal dimension of decision-making. As a policy tool, it strengthens the legitimacy, adaptability and equity of Liveable Neighbourhoods, ensuring that the city’s transition to sustainable mobility is not only implemented for communities, but imagined, tested and shaped with them.

5.3 Copenhagen, DK: Exposing blind spots in a high-capacity planning system through citizen science

The Copenhagen Observatory demonstrates how Citizen Observatories can add public value not by compensating for infrastructural deficits, but by revealing the blind spots that persist even within one of Europe’s most advanced planning systems. Copenhagen’s high-capacity governance model, marked by strong institutional trust, sophisticated mobility planning, and high service performance, creates a paradoxical challenge: because the city functions so well at scale, micro-scale environmental stressors often remain hidden within aggregated datasets. The Copenhagen Observatory was therefore designed as a diagnostic instrument for exposing these overlooked realities. Rather than responding to acute degradation, it interrogates the gaps between official modelling and lived experience, testing how participatory data practices can complement, refine, and occasionally challenge institutional knowledge in a digitally saturated, high-trust context where residents typically require strong incentives to engage. This positioning makes Copenhagen a critical counter-archetype to Bristol pilot, proving that Citizen Observatories are equally relevant for policy innovation and environmental documentation in highly capable urban systems as they are in disadvantaged or underserved settings.

Development unfolded in two phases: an initial period of situated onboarding, in which stakeholders, local concerns, data gaps, and potential use cases were mapped; followed by a shift to active intermediation, which reframed the Observatory as a mediator between municipal planning constraints, methodological validation requirements, and the experiential insights of citizens navigating daily environmental stressors. Because residents of Copenhagen have a high “distance threshold” for participation, satisfied with services, selective about digital engagement, the Observatory concentrated on targeted, high-value interactions with strategic publics, including students, cyclists, and residents of Amager. At the same time, it established a Quadruple Helix governance model positioning public authorities, academic validators, citizen-sensors, and technology providers as co-creators of the city’s environmental intelligence. Traffic planners of local stakeholders engaged with the pilot to test whether citizen-generated Evidence Briefs could justify interventions that macro-statistics failed to detect; KU and BUAs secured methodological credibility; residents and students supplied hyper-local data exposing hyper-local specific environmental conditions; and GREENGAGE partners such as MindEarth, AIT, Atmotube, Digital Sunray, and KWMC brought in tools, transparent workflows, and cross-city comparability. Within this model, the Observatory shifted participation away from generic crowdsourcing and toward a more meaningful proposition: contributing evidence capable of influencing municipal policy.

A defining governance innovation was the GREENGAGE Ambassador Programme, which brought trained volunteers from North Brabant into Amager for intensive noise-mapping missions and later introduced the Conversation Station into the Copenhagen context. This cross-border mobilisation demonstrated that Observatories can operate as transferable infrastructures rather than locality-bound experiments. The success of non-local ambassadors in generating reliable evidence strengthened the credibility of GREENGAGE’s training methodology and signalled the future potential of inter-city civic science alliances. The Conversation Station itself, an agile, artist-designed platform for capturing situated citizen testimony, was explored as a core tool for active intermediation and sentiment capture and tested in collaborative pop-ups in Copenhagen through the Ambassador exchange with Bristol pilot. Functioning as a mobile node for civic dialogue, it bridged technical measurements with qualitative insight, grounding data in the lived experiences of residents and enabling the Observatory to capture concerns in situ rather than through remote surveys.

The Observatory orchestrated three major campaigns that demonstrated its ability to produce “Deep Data” by enabling specificity, resolution, and experiential relevance over sheer quantity. The pilot’s flagship effort, an air quality campaign confirmed Copenhagen’s clean-air profile while revealing exposure-maximising “micro-events” along cycling routes, spikes that static monitors and annual averages cannot capture. The more experimental vertical noise campaign, across building elevations, resumed in the hypotheses that maximum noise events often peaked at top- or mid-level floors due to the Urban Canyon Effect. By integrating these measurements with home-based surveys on disturbance and annoyance, the Observatory produced actionable evidence, not only challenging the assumption that upper floors are quieter and illustrating the need for façade-level interventions but also giving local lived experience and knowledge to current state-of-the-art scientific modelling proposing much higher proportions of residents exposed to harmful noise levels. Meanwhile, the heavy-haulage mobility campaign combined AI-processed cycling videos (validated through Digital Sunray’s comparative modelling) with geolocated perception surveys to demonstrate a significant divergence between official safety metrics and citizens’ feelings of unsafety, an insight with direct implications for road design and freight regulation. Further campaigns, including 360° visual scans for dwell-time analysis, expanded the Observatory’s sensing repertoire and demonstrated the adaptability of volunteers and student teams to more technical assignments.

These campaigns were deliberately structured around adaptive “micro-circuits”, short, manageable routes of four to five points that increased completion rates, protected data quality, and respected the limits of volunteer capacity, particularly during winter-only data windows. In parallel, the pilot has sought to develop a protocol combining statistical methodologies and complementary data sources, e.g. high frequency data of mobile phones, Copernicus data etc. to add large authoritative bodies of data to locally collected data. Together, this effort has demonstrated that these new data sources capture local dynamics as more frequent updates, e.g. deficits between official classification of streets and their actual use. This combined micro-tasking approach exemplified the pilot’s ethos: tailoring scientific design to human realities and demonstrating that methodological rigour grows when citizen science is thoughtfully orchestrated rather than being overly demanding.

The evidence generated across these efforts revealed a new picture of Copenhagen’s environmental landscape, one that distinguishes between the planned city mapped through official models and the lived city captured by citizen sensing. These findings fed directly into policy pipelines. The municipality expressed particular interest in noise and air quality profiles around schools, prompting plans for targeted monitoring of vulnerable zones and strengthening the political salience of the Observatory’s outputs. The formal validation of mobility counts by Digital Sunray removed a major barrier to institutional uptake, demonstrating that citizen-generated video data, processed through YOLO11³, could match the accuracy of established static sensors. Collaboration with CIID signalled an expansion of the city’s stakeholder ecosystem, aiming to translate complex environmental data into interactive formats better suited for public engagement and decision support. Meanwhile, the integration of students into fieldwork required new governance protocols around access rights, data recovery, and monitoring of participation, further embedding Observatory practices within Copenhagen’s educational institutions.

All evidence streams are being consolidated into a Citizen Evidence Brief for the Amager Local Traffic Plan and integrated into shared dashboards that combine subjective perceptions with objective measures, a model of Open Governance that recognises experiential insight as a legitimate dimension of environmental monitoring. By validating the Amager Local Traffic Plan, the pilot demonstrated that citizen-generated data enriches rather than challenges institutional datasets, providing semantic depth to statistical patterns and clarifying why certain stressors, noise, perceived danger, episodic pollution, feel harmful even when they remain invisible at aggregate scales. This reframing strengthens trust, reduces institutional risk, and models a governance culture in which municipalities and residents jointly define environmental priorities.

Through its methodological innovations, campaigns, governance architecture, and policy integrations, the Copenhagen Observatory has broadened the legitimacy of citizen science as a platform for civic innovation, democratic experimentation, and participatory policymaking in the context of a mature urban system. It demonstrates that Observatories are not only mechanisms for addressing deficits but also instruments for refining high-performing systems, bringing local data and knowledge through scientific methods to use in planning and policy processes, and co-creating resilient futures grounded in lived experience, scientific rigour, and democratic values.

5.4 Turano Valley & Gerace, IT: Co-creating data-based pathways for regeneration with innovators from rural communities

The GREENGAGE pilot in the Turano Valley and Gerace demonstrates how Citizen Observatories can become engines of territorial regeneration in digitally fragile, socio-economically isolated rural regions, precisely where participatory governance structures and reliable datasets are scarcest. In a landscape marked by depopulation, limited infrastructure, and fragmented institutional capacity, GREENGAGE’s Observatories served as a strategic framework for transforming citizen science from a technocratic experiment into a participatory governance instrument capable of influencing regeneration policy, attracting investment, and strengthening public trust.

The Observatory implementation began by positioning itself as a public commitment to local revitalisation, introduced through a municipal launch held on 9 March, 2024 that combined institutional visibility with tangible participation via the distribution of air-quality sensors. This early move embodied GREENGAGE’s advocacy aim of creating conditions for local uptake by making the project legible, accessible, and grounded in community needs. Recognising that rural communities face deep digital divides and often-justified scepticism toward outside initiatives, the pilot replaced the “self-service” engagement model typical of urban contexts with an “active intermediation” governance structure. Coordinators were forging trust through door-to-door engagement, interpreting digital tools for participants, and anchoring the Observatory in local cultures of reciprocity and everyday presence. This labour-intensive approach ensured the inclusion of elderly, digitally excluded, and disadvantaged residents, thereby overcoming a structural barrier to participatory governance.

In parallel, the pilot delivered—for the first time ever in the Turano Valley—a structured analysis of local mobility patterns using regional mobility datasets. This work provided new insights into commuting flows and the dynamics of movement to and from the valley. The results proved highly relevant for both public

³ YOLO (You Only Look Once) model, real-time deep learning framework for object detection.

administrations and local organisations, offering evidence that can support transport planning, tourism strategies, and future territorial development actions. By combining environmental monitoring with mobility intelligence, the Turano Observatory demonstrated how data-driven participation can inform decision-making in sparsely populated rural areas.

As the Observatory matured, the pilot performed a strategic shift from problem-detection to asset-based regeneration. Rather than framing the valley as a place with deficits to fix, the Observatory constituted by *I Borghi più Belli d'Italia*, municipal authorities, and residents co-created data that foregrounded environmental quality, cultural richness, and community resilience as foundations for territorial revitalisation. Air-quality sensing confirmed the valley's status as a "green lung," offering not only environmental evidence but a positive narrative capable of motivating residents and strengthening the valley's position within regional tourism and green development strategies. Meanwhile, the mobility analysis and the mobility monitoring through citizen-generated dashcam data created a crowd-sourced inventory of road anomalies and travel behaviour, filling longstanding information gaps that had hindered municipal investment proposals. Cultural heritage mapping generated an archaeological layer that tied regeneration to identity, pride, and economic opportunity, while waste and circular-economy campaigns in Gerace demonstrated how citizen insights can directly shape municipal planning, enabling authorities to view communities not as sources of complaint but as partners producing actionable environmental intelligence.

Through these campaigns, the Observatory exercised a core REENGAGE advocacy function: modelling how citizen data can clarify local conditions better than official datasets alone, thereby reducing institutional risk and strengthening trust. The pilot showed that citizens could provide high-resolution evidence on issues invisible to traditional monitoring, such as the behavioural origins of winter air-pollution peaks or hyper-local waste hotspots, helping municipalities take more precise, politically credible decisions. This advocacy effect deepened as datasets were fed into participatory workshops where scientific analysis, citizen interpretations, and policy ambitions were aligned. In these spaces, new regeneration pathways emerged: linking mobility improvements to digital connectivity, connecting air-quality advantages to sustainable tourism, and integrating cultural-heritage preservation with environmental stewardship.

Over time, the Observatory became woven into local governance structures, demonstrating REENGAGE's proposition that Citizen Observatories can evolve into durable components of participatory policy systems. In the Turano Valley, mobility and travel-demand data supported a regional tender for an electric bus service, an example of citizen evidence directly enabling Green Deal-aligned infrastructure investment. In Gerace, waste mapping informed the creation of a municipal "Green Hub," and circular-economy initiatives reinforced the use of citizen data as a planning tool. The mayor of Castel di Tora's request for a "Guardians of Lake Turano" observatory marked a turning point: for the first time, a local authority commissioned a citizen-monitoring system as an ongoing governance mechanism, not as a project-bounded experiment. Similarly, cultural-mapping outputs fed into plans for a formal Archaeological Path, illustrating how citizen-generated datasets support both economic development and long-term place branding.

These institutional impacts demonstrate the pilot's central advocacy achievement: it showed that Citizen Observatories can help rural administrations articulate evidence-based visions for regeneration, strengthen their capacity to attract regional and EU investments, and create participatory infrastructures that outlive project cycles. Through partnerships across municipalities, universities, regional agencies, and the national Borghi network, the Observatory expanded its influence beyond the valley, culminating in a planned agreement to replicate the model across Italian villages, extending REENGAGE's advocacy reach to a national scale.

By bridging local knowledge with scientific analysis, overcoming barriers to digital participation, and demonstrating how citizen-generated evidence can shape strategic planning, the Turano & Gerace pilot offers a compelling narrative for the broader adoption of Citizen Observatories as tools for participatory governance. It shows that rural regeneration becomes more legitimate, resilient, and actionable when citizens produce the data that defines their future; when authorities see community monitoring as a trusted extension of their own capacity; and when environmental, cultural, and mobility evidence is woven into shared visions of sustainable, liveable, and beautiful places. Through this lens, the pilot stands as a powerful advocacy case for REENGAGE: citizen science not only monitors change - it activates it, accelerates it, and anchors it in the lived experience of those who will inhabit the region's future.

6 Delivering Datathon events to build capacity for the uptake of Observatories:

Datathon events were envisioned as collaborative events where participants gather to analyse data and generate insights within a set period. Beyond just a technical exercise, datathons serve as powerful advocacy tools, raising awareness about important societal issues and mobilising public participation in policy-oriented research. These events enhance participants' data literacy and foster a deeper understanding of the issues, driving public attention and collective action towards a just climate transition. However, as the pilots were embedded in distinctive public engagement processes, these events needed to be tailored to the local socio-political conditions, cultures and states of campaign developments of distinctive Observatories. That's why the pilots re-framed Datathon events and delivered an Ideathon in Turano, and Community Launch and Collective Sensemaking events of Bristol Civic Observatory in Bristol,

6.1 North Brabant: Integrating Datathon activities in the curriculum

The pilot encountered a significant operational friction point regarding the Datathon. Originally planned as a public hackathon to analyze the gathered data, the event faced a critical barrier: delays in the delivery of official provincial datasets needed for comparison.

Rather than cancelling the activity, the pilot team executed a strategic pivot, reconfiguring the Datathon as an integrated curriculum activity within Breda University of Applied Sciences (BUAs). This shift transformed a one-off event into a sustained analytical process. Students utilized the (delayed) data as part of their coursework, performing deep-dive analyses on the correlation between weather, time of day, and subjective scoring. This adaptation not only saved the campaign but embedded the "Citizen Observatory" methodology into the training of future urban planners.

Halfway through December 2025, the first iteration of the Datathon lecture and workshop took place, involving about 35 in the analysis of data gathered in the GREENGAGE Pilot, and the integration into the Provincial Digital Twin. The goals of the Datathon were twofold: Identify relevant auxiliary datasets to complement with the subjective data gathered on bollards or maintenance, and reflect on the use of digital tools such as a digital twin in engaging citizens more strongly in policy making. The participants in the Datathon expressed restraint on the utility of a digital twin as a means to foster citizen participation. While it is a strong tool to visualise data and combine datasets (such as school routes, accident frequency, and road maintenance levels), the tool remained highly dependent on data acuity. This is not a tool that can easily be used by everyone, as the starting threshold consists of knowledge of data analysis. However, the visualisation options work well in convincing a variety of stakeholders. Armed with this critical caveat, the participants of the Datathon are now better prepared for future data and citizen science campaigns.

6.2 Bristol: Community launch of Bristol Civic Observatory and satellites for transdisciplinary sensemaking

The Bristol Datathon activities were designed as collective sensemaking processes, bringing local communities, researchers, and practitioners together to interpret data grounded in lived experience. Given the diversity of communities involved and the range of neighbourhood observation campaigns undertaken, the pilot combined a central Community Launch of the Bristol Civic Observatory with additional, targeted sensemaking sessions tailored to different publics. This approach recognised that no single format could adequately support the breadth of perspectives, data practices, and capacities present across the pilot.

The Community Launch of the Bristol Civic Observatory took place on 16 October 2025 at Wellspring Settlement, a trusted community hub in Barton Hill. Over 50 participants attended throughout the day, representing a wide range of ages, backgrounds, and levels of prior engagement. Participants consistently valued the transparent presentation of data and the opportunity for open discussion on issues directly affecting daily life. Conversations around the Civic Observatory and the East Bristol Liveable Neighbourhood (EBLN) trial generated strong interest and reinforced the importance of community-led dialogue in shaping local decision-making.

Partners played a critical role in the success of the event. KWMC and PRAXIS facilitated trust-building activities through critical mapping, conversation stations, and missions that foregrounded lived experience and collective reflection. AIT, UWE, and other technical partners supported real-time visualisations, thematic analysis, and adaptive tools that were shaped in response to citizen feedback during the event itself. The flexible, multi-workshop format enabled broad participation, allowing attendees to engage at their own pace and according to their interests. Digital tools, including the GREENGAGE app, Conversation Station, and dashboards, were generally well received, particularly by younger participants, who engaged readily with interactive and visual methods.

The event also surfaced important insights into community expectations and constraints. Participants articulated a strong desire for an observatory led by local volunteers, underpinned by transparency, inclusivity, and collective action. While no volunteers formally signed up on the day, there was clear enthusiasm for continued engagement and for the ongoing use of GREENGAGE technologies, alongside expectations that the project would maintain visible support and follow-through. Challenges included the use of technical language within the app, lengthy onboarding processes, memory-related issues in data capture, and varying levels of digital literacy. Some participants expressed a clear preference for analogue tools such as paper maps and face-to-face conversations. Emotional responses to the data highlighted the importance of sensitive facilitation and trauma-aware approaches. Feedback also indicated that participants living outside the core intervention area tended to be more supportive, while previous experiences of consultation influenced levels of trust and willingness to engage.

Despite these challenges, the overall approach proved effective. Targeted pre-event outreach, open-ended questioning, and a listening-first methodology enabled the collection of richer and more nuanced insights than would have been possible through traditional survey-based methods alone. The deliberate combination of analogue and digital tools increased accessibility and positioned GREENGAGE as a transparent and trustworthy platform for community input. The level of engagement and the positive reception of the technology demonstrated clear potential for continued data collection and longer-term impact. Overall, the Community Launch successfully blended tech-enabled insight generation with meaningful community dialogue, laying a strong foundation for the future development of the Bristol Civic Observatory.

In parallel, a series of Community Satellite events were organised to support transdisciplinary sensemaking across the ambassadors-led pilot. These sessions ensured that distinctive datasets generated by different Ambassador groups could be interpreted in accessible and context-sensitive ways. Preliminary AI-supported analyses were shared back with participants, who were actively involved in validating, contextualising, and refining the findings. The methods used varied according to the purposes and practices of each group.

Young people from Bristol Somali Youth Voice (25 November 2025) related collective insights back to their individual experiences through short, self-recorded videos. At Wellspring Settlement and the associated Healthcare Centre, data was discussed in a focused session with the director and communications manager, alongside an artist who delivered training on editing voice-based data for public communication (24 October 2025). Teachers and pupils from Redfield Educate Together engaged in thematic co-exploration of their data (25 September 2025), while members of Bristol East Disabled Society made sense of diary-based campaigns through a storytelling workshop facilitated by artists (28 November 2025).

A preliminary version of a sound art piece, alongside an exhibition documenting the prototyping process of the Bristol Civic Observatory, was shared during a Collective Listening event (9 November 2025). This event brought together local community members, councillors, and researchers, who contributed to the further refinement of the sonic data story and the associated case study that will be published in January 2026. Recordings generated through the Conversation Station during this event will inform future developments beyond the lifetime of GREENGAGE, reinforcing the observatory's role as a shared, evolving civic resource and planning instrument.

6.3 Copenhagen Datathon: Demonstrating citizen evidence towards a shared knowledge base

Due to the coinciding local election and potentially influence to the democratic process, the local stakeholder group asked to postpone the Datathon event to after the election of 18th November 2025. Instead, the pilot arranged a demonstration event after the election 26th November 2025 where data were presented to municipality planners, local council working groups, scientists, a building certification body and architects to expand the knowledge base of the citizen science community to new competence organisations.

6.4 The Turano ‘Ideathon’

The Turano Valley Ideathon emerged from months of preparation that involved identifying suitable datasets, clarifying the Observatory’s objectives, and exploring partnerships for a collective analysis event. Building on earlier discussions about the role of datathons within the Turano Valley Observatory, the pilot shifted from a purely expert-led data analysis format to an “Ideathon” designed to make data interpretation accessible to local participants and meaningful for the region’s revitalization goals.

Held on 27 March 2025 in Castel di Tora, the Ideathon brought together local citizens, mayors, students, and technical experts in a deliberately “vertically integrated” group. Organized in partnership with I Borghi più belli d’Italia and hosted in the Castle of Castel di Tora, the event linked heritage, environmental monitoring, and future development pathways.

The Ideathon used a hybrid methodology that combined fieldwork and co-design. Participants collected air-quality and mobility data using project tools and then analysed these findings together to explore ideas for urban green areas and heritage valorisation. The event also served as a real-world test of data visualisations with local administrators. While the “control room” concept was appreciated, feedback highlighted the need for simpler, narrative-driven dashboards that non-experts can easily interpret.

To support wider participation, the Ideathon introduced a physical, face-to-face data collection point, adapted from Bristol’s approach, to engage residents with low digital literacy. This method, together with new data gathered during the Festival of the Polenta in August 2025 and the creation of an attractiveness perception map, reinforced the Observatory’s commitment to combining citizen-led sensing with local knowledge to shape a shared narrative about the Turano Valley’s future.

7 Challenges for advocating for the uptake of Observatories

The success of advocacy actions lies in pilots shaping public discourse and mobilizing collaborative efforts for a green and just transition through the Observatory's processes and platforms. Effective actions have built narratives that:

- a) foster public support for Observatories by demonstrating their long-term value beyond GREENGAGE, convincing key stakeholders of their relevance, and
- b) engage a wider range of actors in local research and innovation by leveraging the processes and platforms of citizen science initiatives.

To understand the challenges for the realization of envisioned Advocacy actions, but also for the uptake of Observatories by stakeholders and public discourses with policy impact, we undertook reflexive conversations with pilot owners in early February 2025. From these conversations we understood that the challenges, in part, are based in the dynamically evolving situational conditions in the pilot localities and these were addressed in previous reports (e.g., deliverable D5.1).

The following interpretative analysis focussing on how these challenges affected the realization of advocacy actions for the uptake of Observatories is an attempt to tackle their root causes and to address these challenges systemically.

7.1 Building purposeful narratives to interact with publics through Observatories

How we frame Observatories shapes their ability to change “business as usual” in local decision-making. Their public visibility and communication determine whether they can engage diverse stakeholders – a key factor in their long-term adoption. However, the progress in crafting compelling narratives has been hindered by dynamic situational, but also socio-economic and democratic conditions, as well as the local cultures of public engagement and policy innovation. Essentially, we cannot observe the process of policymaking as purely linear. In practice, **policymaking unfolds as a patchwork of networks, projects, and unanticipated events and is inevitably influenced by public discourses.** As Watson (2024) puts it, “any notion that policymaking is systematic and can be planned for is naïve.”

To emphasize this, we refined the GREENGAGE methodology on Observatories (D3.3), highlighting their socio-political embeddedness **as policy and governance labs.** Focussing on their purpose of co-creating situated intelligence - through making sense of crowdsourced data – that is speaking to different publics, we understand that Observatories are deeply intertwined with local cultures of public engagement and policy innovation. To relate to these, Observatories must remain agile in their frameworks, responding to politically significant local events and adapting their engagement strategies accordingly. That's why making sense of such experiments including different local knowledges and sharing conceptualisations in ways that resonate with targeted groups and communities are ongoing required practices in the Observatories' development.

This also affects how we determine stakeholders with political influence. **Policymakers play a role, but so do public discourse, funding bodies, authorities across different levels, (social) media platforms, mobilized citizens, and even technologies.** If Observatories are to endure, they need to become **meaningful to a wide range of people and embedded in their everyday lives.** And to foster inclusion of marginalised groups, they should **not just tackle environmental issues but also addressing their intersections with socio-economic and democratic challenges** (D3.3). While these challenges go beyond our project's scope, securing political buy-in requires us to acknowledge and engage with them in the ways we speak about them.

Long-term vision is essential, but this is not an ever-fixed statement but will evolve through collective learning. In the GREENGAGE pilots, the **narratives that give meaning to the investigations or purpose for action**, have changed since the project beginning as they are co-created in the sense that they incorporate local knowledges from communities and stakeholders. This deliverable presents an updated version of some of the pilot specifications in form of pilot pitches that serve as starting points for further refinements by those on the ground, the storytellers of their Observatories. They will tailor narratives to the specific public discourse arenas in which these planning and development challenges might unfold.

7.2 Aligning Citizen Science initiatives with Observatories' narratives

From the perspective of advocacy actions, there is another challenge that needs to be addressed: ensuring that the framing of the Observatories is fully aligned with the way citizen science initiatives have been developed within them. **While the Observatory is described as a space for shaping public discourse and engagement, the citizen science initiatives are intended to test, demonstrate, and refine data-based narratives for change.** This alignment is essential for maintaining coherence between the Observatories' participatory methodologies and their public representation, reinforcing their legitimacy, and strengthening their role as instruments for policy innovation and civic engagement.

It equally shapes how people understand their role in the process and how the interpretation of the data that is collected is carried out. It should not be assumed that producing data automatically leads to change, when in reality, the data needs to be connected with public discourse and civic action. To address this, **we align the planned experiments and the related data with the storylines of each pilot – clarifying the element of change they aim to create and how they seek to engage citizens in policymaking.** A 'What If' analysis can help facilitate this process, ensuring that citizen science initiatives are designed to support the Observatory's overall narrative. This is why we see the pilot pitches in this deliverable as an important step in informing the general thematic co-explorations' development as part of the long-term uptake of the GOs.

By making this shift, we can better demonstrate the value of Observatories - not just as platforms for environmental data collection, but as spaces for collective action, policy innovation, and new forms of citizen participation. This seems to be especially relevant to **fully align our experiments with Green Deal objectives and to make our initiatives more meaningful for marginalised, seldomly heard or historically underrepresented groups and communities in policy making and local governance.** By refining our approach in this way, we can strengthen the role of Observatories as innovative tools for systemic change.

7.3 Data for active intermediation: Enhancing analysis and visualization for public engagement through Observatories

A key aspect of effective advocacy activities is **clarity on topic-specific data sources and crowdsourcing needs**, which serve as the foundation of robust analysis and visualization of local conditions. This, in turn, helps to identify and address critical issues aligned with the goals of the European Green Deal, further helping identification and engagement of key actors, ranging from policymakers and local authorities to community groups and researchers. This clarity gives the project the advantage point to develop data visualisation solutions fully guided by a clear vision of the pilot owners who know how they can and want to engage with influential publics around crowdsourced data.

8 Conclusions

The journey of developing and implementing GREENGAGE Observatories has been both ambitious and complex, shaped by a continuous interplay between structured innovation and the fluid realities of local engagement. As we reflect on this process, it becomes clear that while Observatories have started engaging with diverse publics, they not yet ignited public discourse, amplified diverse voices, and driven governance and policy debates. We understood that they have also encountered significant hurdles, driven by dynamically changing local situations. These challenges offer crucial lessons that can guide future efforts in ensuring Observatories are not just experimental initiatives but sustainable, impactful, and deeply embedded in civic ecosystems.

To build momentum and strengthen impact, GREENGAGE will continue pursuing storytelling-driven dissemination and interactive knowledge exchange as key approaches in making insights accessible, actionable, and engaging for wider audiences. The road ahead is one of co-creation, where technology, storytelling, and civic action converge to shape more inclusive, resilient, and community-led futures.

9 Annexes

9.1 Guideline for Organising Datathons

Why do a datathon?

A datathon is a collaborative event where participants gather to analyse data and generate insights within a set period. Beyond just a technical exercise, datathons serve as powerful advocacy tools, raising awareness about important societal issues and mobilising public participation in policy-oriented research. In the context of Greengage, datathons empower citizens to engage with real-world data while actively advocating for positive change. These events enhance participants' data literacy and foster a deeper understanding of the issues, driving public attention and collective action towards a just climate transition. Common goals that can be achieved through datathons are:

- Increase civic engagement in scientific data analysis.
- Advocate for citizen-led data initiatives, collective civic goals and community concerns through storytelling.
- Contribute to evidence-based public policy discussions and policy making.
- Enhance data literacy and teamwork among participants.

Define objectives

Before starting a datathon, defining what you expect of it is essential. This implies defining its purpose (e.g., addressing urban challenges, advancing AI applications, etc.) and its scope (e.g., specifying whether the datathon is exploratory (insights) or solution-driven (models/tools)). Ideally, the purpose and scope should be connected to the specific urban challenge addressed by each GREENGAGE Observatory. In other words, the outcome of the datathons should be instrumental for the Observatory goals as well as current and future work.

The success of the datathon relies mainly on providing access to a well-structured dataset with which participants can analyse and extract insights or innovative results. This data set should be related to a challenge answering to the purpose of the datathon. In GREENGAGE, datathons are advocacy activities that foster the Observatories' data and results uptake. In this sense, some possible purposes can be:

- Generate insights from data sets produced by participants of the Observatories in relation to a specific local planning challenge.
- Gain new practical understandings from analysing data produced by Observatories combined with authoritative or already existing data sets.
- Generate insights from authoritative or public datasets that can complement already existing or future research and advocacy activities of the Observatories.

The purpose and scope will help you to identify the goal of the datathon more clearly. Examples can be:

- **Air Pollution Monitoring:** How can we use sensor-based air quality data to identify our city's most polluted areas and hours? What patterns or sources contribute to spikes in pollution, and what solutions can be proposed to improve air quality? Who is more vulnerable to pollution spikes?
- **Sustainable Mobility:** What are the current patterns of transportation usage, and how can we optimise routes to reduce congestion and emissions? How can data help promote the adoption of sustainable transport options like cycling, walking, or public transit?

- **Urban life conditions:** How can we measure the quality of life through data on housing, green spaces, or public services? How can we design data-driven improvements to enhance community well-being?

Assemble the organising team

You will need a team to support you in preparing and implementing datathons. Some basic roles to take into account can be:

- Event coordinators
- Technical support (virtual platforms, IT)
- Data providers (domain experts, partners)
- Mentors and judges

If you are considering having in-person and virtual activities simultaneously, include team members who are experienced in facilitating hybrid events.

Collaborate with scientific institutions, universities, government agencies, or tech companies to provide expertise and visibility. Building strong partnerships is crucial to the success of your datathon, as it can provide the necessary resources, expertise, and visibility to drive impactful results. Engaging a diverse range of partners can also help ensure long-term sustainability and community engagement. When selecting and working with partners, consider the following categories:

Scientific and Research Institutions: Universities and research institutes bring academic credibility and provide access to specialised knowledge and experts in fields such as environmental science, urban planning, public health, and data science. Partnering with local environmental science departments to guide air pollution monitoring efforts or collaborate with urban planning faculties on the liveability of urban areas. These institutions can also contribute mentors or judges for the datathon, ensuring the scientific rigour of the work produced.

Government Agencies: Collaborating with municipalities or national government bodies (e.g., Departments of Transportation, Environmental Protection Agencies) can provide access to official data that might not be readily available to the public. A local environmental agency might provide air quality datasets for monitoring pollution or support the datathon through access to data on traffic flows for sustainable mobility. Governments can also help implement the findings of the datathon by using the results to shape policy or improve public services.

Civic and Community Organizations: Collaborating with local **citizen groups, community organizations, or neighbourhood associations** ensures that the datathon is grounded in the real concerns of the communities it seeks to impact. A neighbourhood association can, for instance, help shape the problems that focus on making a particular area more livable or safer by providing insights on local challenges like crime, traffic safety, or access to green spaces.

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs): NGOs can amplify the advocacy aspects of the datathon, ensuring that data-driven insights lead to action. Organisations focusing on reducing air pollution or promoting sustainable mobility to help translate datathon findings into advocacy campaigns, public awareness, or actionable policy recommendations. NGOs can also help with community engagement, connecting the datathon with local citizen science networks, volunteers, or activist groups who are passionate about improving their neighbourhoods.

Private Sector and Corporate Sponsors: Corporate partners in sectors related to urban planning, transportation, energy, or technology may be interested in supporting datathons aligned with their corporate social responsibility (CSR) goals. A company involved in sustainable urban mobility might sponsor the event, provide resources, and even implement the best solutions for creating safer streets

or enhancing mobility. Sponsors can offer financial support, prizes for the winning teams, and opportunities for participants to gain internships or career development in data science, sustainability, or urban innovation.

Prepare the data and tools

Before the actual datathon, you must prepare your data sets and the tools used to access and analyse the data. Some critical criteria in this sense are:

- The data should be accessible, relevant, and well-organized. Ensure it aligns with the purpose and goals you want to achieve. Ensure datasets are available to all participants in advance. Identify which secure cloud storage platforms you will use (Google Drive, Dropbox, or others). Define if you need further collaboration platforms: GitHub or Kaggle for sharing code and workflows.
- Data should be standardised (clean, labelled datasets with metadata). Choose the formats in which data will be offered (e.g. CSV, JSON, etc.). Provide tools such as software (e.g., Python, R), cloud resources, or data platforms (e.g., Kaggle, Google Colab).
- Choose the participants: Define the type of participant you want to target. Usually, participants are students who can link their academic activities and pedagogical process to the event challenge or problem. However, you may also want to bring together interested lay citizens. Define whether the reach will be local, national, or international.
- Clarify the participation type: datathons usually encourage or require participants to form teams. This promotes collaboration, idea exchange, and leveraging diverse skills. Teams can range from 2-6 participants. In team-oriented events, individuals who don't have a team can often find one through matchmaking sessions.
- Ensure participants have access to tutorials and guides in advance. Some useful guidelines are:

As part of the preparation, you may need to select other tools and platforms. If you are organising a virtual or hybrid platform, consider tools for the following:

- Communication: define how to communicate with participants and your organisation team. WhatsApp, Slack, or MS Teams are possible options.
- Video Conferencing: Ensure everyone has access to Zoom, Google Meet, or MS Teams for live sessions. Also, ensure they support the number of participants you intend to bring.
- Venue Setup: assure reliable internet connectivity for streaming and collaboration, AV equipment for presentations and live streaming, and dedicated stations for hybrid team discussions (with mics and cameras) are essential.
- Virtual Setup: Remember to have a backup internet connection and tech support for virtual tools. It may also be good to record key sessions for asynchronous access.

Prepare submission and judging

It is important to have some submission guidelines: They are meant to clarify the expectations for the final deliverables (e.g. code, data visualisations, insights, and a report). The submission guideline should define the **submission format** (e.g. GitHub repositories, Jupyter notebooks, or PDFs).

Remember to include some judging criteria. Some standard criteria are:

- Quality of the analysis: How well does it address the scientific question?

- Creativity and innovation: Were unique techniques used?
- Clarity: Is the approach well-documented and easy to follow?
- Potential for real-world impact: How can the findings contribute to science or society?

Ensure transparency in the evaluation process by sharing criteria in advance.

You should also appoint an evaluation panel to evaluate the submissions. The panel can include organisation team members, scientists, data experts, and campaign sponsors.

Design the schedule

Datathons typically last from 1 day to 3 days, depending on the complexity of the problem or challenge addressed. These are suggested activities to be considered in timeline planning:

- **Pre-event phase:**
 - Announcement
 - Registration
 - Kick-off webinar to explain rules, datasets, tools, and hybrid workflows.
 - Tutorials/workshops (e.g., on machine learning or data visualisation).
 - Data access opening
- **During the event:**
 - Opening Ceremony: Live-streamed or hybrid, with an inspiring keynote.
 - Working Hours:
 - Allow flexible schedules to accommodate different time zones.
 - Provide hybrid teams with breakout rooms (both physical and virtual).
 - Mentorship Slots: Schedule 1-on-1 or group sessions with mentors.
 - Checkpoints: Encourage progress sharing and mid-event feedback.
 - Networking Breaks: Virtual and in-person opportunities to connect.
- **Post-event:**
 - Submission deadline for projects.
 - Final presentations (live streamed for remote participants).
 - Awards ceremony.

Preparing for the datathon

Registration:

- Use a platform like Eventbrite or a dedicated registration form.
- Ask for information on participants' skill levels, interests, and team preferences.

Data Release

- Release data a few days before the event so participants can familiarise with it.
- Provide clear documentation about the dataset: context, variables, format, and potential challenges.

Participant onboarding

- Create a welcome guide explaining the rules, data, available tools, and objectives.
- Organize a pre-event workshop or webinar to introduce the scientific problem, data analysis methods, and expectations.

Team Formation

- Allow participants to form teams based on skills and interests.
- Use online tools like Slack, Discord, or Trello to facilitate team communication.

Mentors and Experts

- Assign mentors or experts (from the scientific community, data science field, or sponsors) to provide guidance during the datathon.

Running the Datathon

Opening event

- Kick off the event with a welcome session.
- Present the scientific problem, available data, and goals.
- Introduce the agenda, rules, and key milestones.
- Encourage participants to network and engage with mentors.
- Define communication channels open for support, motivation, and team coordination.
- Announce the submission deadline.

Data analysis

- Work on analysing the data, developing models, and answering the research question.
- Organize checkpoints where teams can present their progress and ask questions.
- Provide technical support and ensure all participants can access tools and resources.

Awards and Recognition

- Recognize the top-performing teams with awards (prizes, certificates, or internships).
- Highlight notable contributions useful for future research or public use.
- Share the results with participants and the public.
- Publish findings in blogs, newsletters, or scientific publications.
- Conduct a survey to gather participant feedback to improve future events.
- These events are an opportunity to create a community to continue collaboration and learning. You may also encourage participants to stay involved in the Observatory or joining future activities

9.2 Conceptualisations for Storybuilding on the Project level

STORY no. 01

Storyboard Concept: "The Power of Many – How Citizen Observatories Enable Participatory Governance"

1. Opening Scene: The Challenge of Environmental Policy

Visuals: A bustling European city with air pollution, traffic congestion, and rising temperatures. Overlay of graphs and statistics showing environmental concerns.

Voiceover: "Europe and its cities face pressing environmental challenges. But how can policies reflect the needs and realities of local communities to improve their everyday life?"

2. Introducing the Citizen Observatory Model

Visuals: Citizens using mobile apps, low-cost sensors, and online platforms to report issues such as air quality, noise levels, and mobility patterns. A digital map lights up with real-time data.

Voiceover: "The Citizen Observatory model enables local communities to actively collect, share, and interpret data from their surroundings, transforming them from passive observers into engaged contributors who drive local improvements and informed decision-making."

3. How GREENGAGE Empowers Citizens to be Advocates for Policy Change

Visuals: A GREENGAGE dashboard where policymakers view community-generated insights. A workshop where citizens, scientists, and officials discuss findings.

Voiceover: "By adopting the Citizen Observatory model, GREENGAGE empowers citizens to be the voice of their communities, generating actionable knowledge about their surroundings and advocating for policy change, while fostering a sense of purpose and ownership in the development and well-being of their neighborhoods."

5. A Better Future for All with Participatory Governance

Visuals: A European Commission meeting, where officials acknowledge the impact of citizen-driven data to adjust urban policies. A vision of future cities co-designed by residents and policymakers.

Voiceover: "By valuing local knowledge and contributions, we can create smarter, more inclusive policies that better serve and benefit all members of the community."

STORY no. 02

Storyboard Concept: "GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories Tackling Local Challenges"

1. Opening Scene: A Shared Challenge with a Local Approach

Visuals: A dynamic split-screen showing five European pilot areas with different environmental challenges. Data overlays highlight concerns such as poor air quality, safety measures, and traffic congestion.

Voiceover: "Environmental challenges cross borders, but solutions begin at the local level. GREENGAGE is establishing Citizen Observatories in five pilot areas, empowering local residents to become active contributors to a meaningful change."

2. Setting up GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories

Visuals: People receiving sensors, setting up environmental monitors, and accessing the GREENGAGE digital platform on their phones. Local workshops bring together citizens, researchers, and policymakers.

Voiceover: "The Citizen Observatory model enables local communities to actively collect, share, and interpret data from their surroundings, transforming them from passive observers into engaged contributors who drive local improvements and informed decision-making."

3. Observing and Collecting Data

Visuals: Citizens measuring air quality, monitoring safety levels, and tracking traffic patterns. A real-time dashboard updates with community-generated data.

Voiceover: "With user-friendly technology, people can gather real-world insights, creating a shared understanding of their local environment and challenges."

4. From Data to Action: Participatory Governance

Visuals: A public meeting where residents, scientists, and policymakers discuss findings. Decisions are made based on real data, such as implementing green zones or improving public transport.

Voiceover: "By communicating data-driven insights to decision-makers, GREENGAGE empowers communities to shape policies and drive meaningful change, ensuring smarter, community-driven decisions."

5. A Future of Co-Created Citizen Observatories

Visuals: A transformed neighborhood with improved mobility, cleaner air, and engaged citizens. A map expands beyond the five pilot areas, showing a vision for Europe-wide adoption where citizens continue monitoring, discussing, and shaping their environments.

Voiceover: "Citizen Observatories are more than just tools - they are a new way of governance. With GREENGAGE, the future of participatory decision-making starts today."

STORY no. 03

Storyboard Concept: "GREENGAGE Empowering Communities through Citizen Observatories"

1. Local Communities Taking Action

Visuals: Five EU pilot areas with residents actively engaging in environmental monitoring. A title overlay: "GREENGAGE: Empowering Communities through Citizen Observatories."

Voiceover: "What if citizens could shape policies with real-world data? Across five European pilot areas, communities are collecting valuable insights to better understand their environment and influence decision-making."

2. The Hands-On Approach: Citizens Observing & Monitoring

Visuals: Residents in each pilot area engage in real-time data collection activities. Urban volunteers mount air quality sensors on lampposts and measure pollution near schools and busy roads. Suburban residents use image-mapping apps to assess the state of the road infrastructure.

Voiceover: "Through accessible technology, communities collect meaningful data, making their observations count."

3. From Data to Understanding: Making Sense of the Numbers

Visuals: A GREENGAGE digital dashboard updates in real-time with incoming citizen data. Residents compare their findings to historical trends, uncovering patterns and anomalies. Scientists and policymakers join workshops to interpret the results, linking local observations to broader environmental shifts.

Voiceover: "With the help of digital tools and expert insights, raw data turns into valuable knowledge - helping communities grasp the changes happening in their own backyards."

4. Driving Policy Change: Citizens & Policymakers Collaborate

Visuals: A town hall meeting where residents present findings to decision-makers and advocate for better climate adaptation measures. A policymaker references citizen-collected air quality data to adjust traffic flow, improve the road infrastructure and connectivity.

Voiceover: "By bringing data to the decision-making table, communities ensure their voices are heard in shaping policies that affect them."

5. Scaling Up: A New Era of Participatory Governance

Visuals: A zoom-out reveals a growing network of Citizen Observatories across Europe, with interconnected data streams, engaged communities, and policymakers working alongside citizens. Residents continue monitoring their environment, attending workshops, and influencing local decisions.

Voiceover: "The REENGAGE project is proving that when citizens observe, monitor, and understand their neighbourhoods, governance becomes truly participatory. This is just the beginning - what will your community uncover?"

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

10 References

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